

The Chemistry of *Securinega* Alkaloids

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From *Securinega suffruticosa* (Pall.) Rehd (Fam. Euphorbiaceae), grown in Rongo, North Bengal, an alkaloid, allosecurinine, has been isolated. The chemistry of allosecurinine, its stereo-configuration, and biogenesis have been discussed.

The alkaloid, securinine, was first isolated from the leaves of *Securinega suffruticosa* (Pall.) Rehd (Fam. Euphorbiaceae) by the Russian workers¹⁻². It has since been the subject of a number of chemical investigations³⁻⁴, extending to other *Securinega* species, viz., *S. virosa*⁵ Pax. et. Hoffm. Previous work has shown that securinine, m.p. 142-43°, $[\alpha]_D^{20} -104.2^\circ$ (EtOH), exhibits $\lambda_{max}^{CCl_4}$ 5.44, 5.69 (=CO), and 6.09 μ (-C=C-) and λ_{max}^{EtOH} 256 m μ (log ϵ , 4.27). The nature of the heterocyclic ring system in securinine was elucidated in the following way. Zinc dust distillation of this alkaloid afforded *p*-toluidine, identified as acetate, m.p. 143-45°, together with ammonia and phenol. Catalytic hydrogenation of this base under different conditions afforded different products. Thus with Raney nickel in aqueous alkali, securinine furnished a lactam carbinol, C₁₃H₁₁O₂N, m.p.

184°, $[\alpha]_D^{27} +3^\circ$ (EtOH), λ_{max} 2.97 and 6.11 μ (N-C=), and no ultraviolet absorption. Dehydrogenation of the lactam carbinol with Pd/C yielded *o*-tolylpyridine, identified as picrate, m.p. 142-43°. When reduced with PtO₂/EtOH or Pd-C/AcOH, securinine provided dihydrosecurinine, C₁₃H₁₇O₂N, m.p. 59-60°, $[\alpha]_D^{22} \pm 0^\circ$ (EtOH), $\lambda_{max}^{CHCl_3}$ 5.40, 5.65 (=CO) and 6.07 μ (-C=C-). The dihydrosecurinine on further reduction with PtO₂/EtOH afforded tetrahydrosecurinine, C₁₃H₁₉O₂N, m.p. 67-68°, $[\alpha]_D^{12} +21.5^\circ$ (EtOH), $\lambda_{max}^{CHCl_3}$ 5.55 μ (=CO). Tetrahydrosecurinine did not exhibit any characteristic UV absorption.

On the basis of these evidences Saito *et al.*³ assigned structure (I) for securinine, stereospecific synthesis of which has just been accomplished⁶.

1. Muraveva and Ban'kovskii, *Doklady Akad. Nauk, S.S.S.R.*, 1956, 110, 998.
2. Bobokhbdzhaev., *Farmakol. I. Toksikol.*, 1957, 20/1, Suppl., 3-5.
3. *Chem. & Ind.*, 1962, 1652.
4. Mukherjee *et al.*, *Naturwiss.*, 1963, 50, 155.
5. Nakano *et al.*, *Chem & Ind.*, 1962, 1651; *Tetrahedron*, 1963, 19, 609.
6. Saito *et al.*, *Chem. Pharm. Bull. Japan*, 1963, 11, 1219.

A new alkaloid was obtained along with a trace of securinine* from the same plant species, grown in Rango, North Bengal, and its occurrence and difference in properties from those of securinine were reported* in 1962. The authors, however, retained the name "Securinine" for the base at that time. Further studies on this alkaloid have revealed that it is possibly a stereoisomer of securinine and it has subsequently been substantiated from a comparison of our sample with allosecurinine, isolated by Dr. Z. Horii and his collaborators.

FIG. 1. I.R. spectra.

*Presence of securinine could only be detected by paper chromatography and TLC.

The statement concerning the chemistry of securinine by the present investigators is henceforth modified by the substitution of the name "Allosecurinine" instead of "Securinine".

All allosecurinine, $C_{13}H_{15}O_2N$, m.p. 128° , shows a parent peak in the mass spectrum at m/e 217, which establishes its molecular formula. The base does not contain any -OMe, -OH, -NMe, and -CMe, functions. The nitrogen atom is tertiary in nature: no characteristic -NH absorption in the IR spectrum and ready formation of a monomethiodide. The two oxygen atoms of this base constitute an $\alpha\beta$ -unsaturated- γ -lactone, as evidenced from its IR spectrum: band at 5.56 and 5.75μ . Appearance of two very sharp bands at 6.16 and 11.77μ reveals the presence of an ethylenic unsaturation in the molecule. The presence of the ethylenic linkage, extending to the conjugation of the $\alpha\beta$ -unsaturated- γ -lactone system⁷ of the alkaloid, was further confirmed from its UV absorption maximum at $255 m\mu$, which remained unchanged in both acid and alkali media, and the shoulder at $320 m\mu$, present in the original base, disappeared in acid solution.

Allosecurinine, on reduction with sodium borohydride in dry methanol, furnished a dihydro derivative, $C_{13}H_{17}O_2N$, m.p. 91° . This base shows an absorption maximum in the UV region at $213 m\mu$. The pronounced hypsochromic shift (by $42 m\mu$) observed in dihydroallosecurinine could only be due to reduction of the ethylenic linkage, originally present in the parent alkaloid. This is also indicated in the IR spectrum of the reduced product in which the lactone carbonyl appears at 5.55 and 5.78μ with the disappearance of the absorption peak at 6.09μ for ethylenic linkage. The NMR data of dihydroallosecurinine are also consistent with these observations. Thus the group of peaks at 6.53 to 7.0δ , present in allosecurinine due to olefinic protons, disappeared in dihydroallosecurinine.

(II)

The alkaloid on reduction with the Adams catalyst in ethanol furnished a hexahydro derivative, later found to be identical with the lactone carbinol (II), obtained from securinine⁸. A singular characteristic feature of allosecurinine is its reluctance to form any tetrahydro derivative under different conditions of reduction. This observation definitely establishes its difference in properties from securinine⁸ and virosecurinine⁸, reported by earlier workers, and eventually indicates its identity with Satoda's allosecurinine⁸ (=phyllchrysin⁹). Hexahydroallosecurinine showed no UV absorption, but two very distinct peaks in the IR spectrum at 3.01 and 6.19μ , ascribed to hydroxyl and lactam groups respectively. The hydroxyl group is tertiary in nature as it forms no acetyl or benzoyl derivative. The formation of the lactam carbinol (II) together with other relevant

7. Connolly and Overton, *Proc. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 188.

8. Satoda et al., *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1962, No. 25, 1199.

9. Parelo et al., *Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1963, 898.

FIG. 3. N.M.R. spectrum of dihydroallosecurinine in CDCl_3 (60M.C; Internal ref. SiMe_4).

data points to a structure similar to (I) for allosecurinine. The difference in properties between securinine and allosecurinine is therefore ascribed to the difference in steric configurations of these two bases. Both the yield and the rapidity of formation of the lactam carbinol (II) are consistent with the transient nature of the tetrahydro-base and could be due to the hydrogen at C₂, the bridge between B-C ring and the C₇-hydrogen being on the same side of the plane.

The NMR spectrum of allosecurinine taken in CDCl₃ supports the foregoing contentions that C₂-C₇ are *cis*, as evidenced from the chemical shifts between 1.2 to 1.8δ.

A very interesting observation with allosecurinine helped to a great extent in assigning the correct structure to it. The alkaloid on treatment with Zn dust and EtOH- H₂SO₄ provided a lactam, C₁₃H₁₅ON, the formation of which was essentially a process of electron displacement from zinc to the positively charged nitrogen through the unsaturated γ-lactone system. The allylic C₇-N₁ bond was thereby hydrogenated, giving rise to the formation of an aromatic ring. This type of aromatisation was reported earlier by Ohashi *et al.*¹⁰. The UV absorption spectrum of the lactam shows maxima at 266 and 272 mμ, typical of a 1,2-disubstituted benzenoid derivative and this has finally been proved from the permanganate oxidation of the lactam (III) to phthalic acid. Reduction of the lactam with LiAlH₄ furnished a basic oil, which formed a solid hydrochloride, C₁₃H₁₆NCl. The hydrochloride shows characteristic peaks at 265 and 273 mμ in the UV region. It was subsequently proved to be identical with an authentic sample of 1,2,3,4,6,7-hexahydro-11 b *H*-benzo(a)quinolizine (IV) hydrochloride¹¹, kindly supplied by Dr. T. Nakano.

In addition to *S. suffruticosa*, another species, viz., *S. virosa* Pax. et Hoffm., belonging to the genus *Securinega*, was examined by Nakano and his associates⁵. Investigation of *S. virosa* led to the isolation of a new alkaloid, virosecurinine. The structure elucidation and direct comparison of the properties of this alkaloid with those of securinine reveal that the two bases are antipodal.

(III)

(IV)

Nakano *et al.*¹², Parello *et al.*⁹, and Saito and his research group^{13,14} have been trying to elucidate the correct absolute configurations of the *Securinega* bases. Varied suggestions are forthcoming and we deem it necessary to record here our appraisal of the assigned steric configurations to securinine, allosecurinine, and virosecurinine and their impact on the possibility of occurrence of another new congener of these bases.

10. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, **81**, 6339.

11. Akaboshi *et al.*, *Chem. Pharm. Bull. Japan*, 1960, **8**, 14.

12. *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1963, No. 10, 665.

13. Saito *et al.*, *Chem. & Ind.*, 1963, 689.

14. Horii *et al.*, *Chem. Pharm. Bull. Japan*, 1962, **11**, 817; I.U.P.A.C. Symposium on Natural Products, Kyoto, Japan, 1964, p. 63.

Securinine contains three asymmetric centres: C_2 , C_7 , and C_9 , but the restriction imposed on by the bridged ring system permits only four (two racemic pairs) of the eight possible optical isomers demanded by the two-dimensional projection (I). Nakano *et al.*¹¹ assigned the following absolute configurational structures (V-VII) to the three compounds, virosecurinine and securinine, the ($\pm$) pair, and allosecurinine respectively.

It is quite possible that besides compounds (V-VII), an alkaloid (VIII), possessing enantiomorphic configuration of allosecurinine (VII), would be existing in nature. That the hydrogen atoms of the two asymmetric carbons C_2 , C_7 and the bridge C_7 - C_9 are all *trans* and more hindered might be a reason for the relative rarity of this alkaloid.

In a previous communication⁴, we reported the mass spectra of allosecurinine, dihydroallosecurinine, and hexahydroallosecurinine and assigned the intense peak at m/e 84 in the mass spectrum of allosecurinine to the presence of a piperidyl moiety. It is intended now to explain the significance of other strong peaks in allosecurinine and its derivatives and their bearing on the origin of the *Securinega* alkaloids.

Aside from the molecular ion peak (m/e 217), there are two important peaks in the mass spectrum of allosecurinine, which can be assigned with such certainty as to detect the major building units of the parent molecule. Species $C_8H_6O_2^+$ (m/e 134) and $C_7H_6O^+$ (m/e 106) occur in the mass spectrum of this base and are expected to be formed by the fragmentation of ring B. These two species are represented by the butenolide (A) and oxycyclobutene (B) moieties, respectively.

The mass spectrum of hexahydroallosecurinine shows an intense peak at $M-28$ due to the loss of CO and that of dihydroallosecurinine at $M-44$ due to the loss of CO_2 from an unsaturated lactone.

Turning now to the mass spectrum of tetrahydrosecurinine⁹, the important peak of allosecurinine m/e 134 is now shifted to m/e 138 (4 mass unit difference due to as many hydrogen atoms), indicating a species $C_8H_{12}O_2^+$ and a structure (C) for the fragment.

By utilising largely the above mass spectrometric fragmentation patterns, coupled with the tenets of alkaloid biogenesis, it is possible now to suggest a route to the genesis

of these alkaloids. One of the distinctive features emerging from the above findings is that for each orientation (α - or β -) of the C_2 -H, there are two possible ways of approach from N_1 to C_7 (above or below the plane of the molecule), assuming prior formation of the C_9 - C_2 bond (moiety E, Chart I) resulting in the bases (V-VIII).

Probable biogenetic sequence of the *Securinega* alkaloids is epitomized below.

CHART I

The butenolide structure occurs in many natural products. Several antibiotics are relatively simple derivatives of this type. Perhaps the moiety (D) in securinine and its isomers is responsible for the reported divergent physiological activity of these bases.

(IX)

Incidentally, suffruticodina, $C_{13}H_{15}O_3N$, a recently reported¹⁵ optically inactive alkaloid found in *S. suffruticosa* and isolated from the mother liquors remaining after the

15. Muraveva and Kuzovkov, *Zhur. Obshch. Khim.*, 1963, **33**, 603.

isolation of securinine, could be (IX) on the basis of its reported chemical properties and from biogenetic considerations. Co-occurrence of this base and securinine in the same species is a strong circumstantial evidence for their genesis from common biogenetic precursors.

EXPERIMENTAL

Isolation of Allosecurinine(I).—Air-dried, powdered roots (2 kg.) of *Securinea suffruticosa* were defatted with light petroleum (b.p. 60-80°) and then Soxhletted (40 hr.) with chloroform (5 litres). From the concentrated chloroform extract (500ml) the basic component was removed with 10% H₂SO₄ (5 × 100ml). The cooled acid solution was made alkaline with ammonium hydroxide, when the free yellow base was liberated. It was taken up in chloroform (400 ml), washed with water, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate, and concentrated. The concentrate was chromatographed over Brockmann alumina (750g.), which was eluted with ether when pure allosecurinine migrated. The ether eluates were freed of the solvent and crystallised from ether when allosecurinine was obtained in shining yellow needles, m.p. 128°, yield 0.42%. (Found: C, 71.55; H, 6.61; N, 6.66; H⁺, 0.00. C₁₃H₁₅O₂N requires C, 71.88; H, 6.90; N, 6.45%). *R*_f = 0.36 (butanol: formic acid: water = 12 : 1 : 7).

The acidity of the base allosecurinine and its molecular weight were determined from potentiometric titrations. (M.W. 210; *p**k* = 7.12). Molecular weight was further confirmed from mass spectrometric data (Mass number = 217).

Allosecurinine hydrochloride was prepared by passing dry HCl gas to a cold solution of allosecurinine in absolute ether. The hydrochloride precipitated was crystallised from rectified spirit in cubes, m.p. 248° (decomp.); [α]_D²⁰ = -33.5° (EtOH). [Found: C, 61.24; H, 6.21; N, 5.61; Cl, 14.13. C₁₃H₁₅O₂N.HCl requires C, 61.53; H, 6.31; N, 5.52; Cl, 14.01%].

Allosecurinine hydroiodide was prepared by adding hydroiodic acid dropwise to a cooled solution of the base in dry methanol, followed by its crystallisation from methanol-ether mixture in needles, m.p. 216° (decomp.). (Found: C, 45.32; H, 4.74; N, 4.21; I, 36.63. C₁₃H₁₅O₂N.HI requires C, 45.22; H, 4.67; N, 4.06; I, 36.81%].

Allosecurinine picrate was prepared in the usual way by adding an ethanolic picric acid solution to an ethanolic solution of allosecurinine. The picrate crystallised in beautiful yellow needles from rectified spirit, m.p. 231-32° (decomp.). (Found: C, 51.48; H, 4.40; N, 12.65. C₁₉H₁₈O₆N₄ requires C, 51.12; H, 4.04; N, 12.56%].

Allosecurinine Methiodide.—To a cooled methanolic solution of the base methyl iodide was added. The methiodide precipitated was crystallised from rectified spirit in clusters, m.p. 235-36° (decomp.). (Found: C, 46.35; H, 4.89; N, 3.92; NMe, 3.66. C₁₃H₁₅O₂N. MeI requires C, 46.79; H, 5.01; N, 3.89; NMe, 4.17%].

Reduction of Allosecurinine with Sodium Borohydride.—To a solution of allosecurinine (0.5 g.) in dry methanol was added sodium borohydride (0.25 g.) at ten instalments. The temperature was maintained at 0°. After final addition, the reaction mixture was kept overnight at 0°. Excess methanol was removed under suction; the product was diluted with water and acidified. Basification of the acid solution liberated dihydroallosecurinine

which was taken up in chloroform. The chloroform digest was worked up in the usual manner, concentrated, and chromatographed over alumina. The benzene-ether eluates (1:4) provided 0.15g. of dihydroallosecurinine which was further purified by sublimation *in vacuo* (108-10°/0.01mm). The white sublimate crystallised from light petroleum (b.p. 40-60°) in needles, m.p. 91°. $\lambda_{\max}^{\text{EtOH}}$ 213 m μ (log ϵ , 4.33). 85.72 (CDCl₃) for vinyl proton at C-12. [Found: C, 70.83; H, 7.94; N, 6.68; H, 0.00. C₁₃H₁₇O₂N requires C, 71.23; H, 7.76; N, 6.39%].

Catalytic Hydrogenation of Allosecurinine to Lactam Carbinol (II).—Allosecurinine (0.5 g.) in ethanol on hydrogenation with the Adams catalyst (0.15 g.) showed an uptake of 3 moles of hydrogen. The reduction product was taken in chloroform and chromatographed over deactivated alumina. The ether-methanol mixture (19:1) eluted fractions on evaporation furnished a solid (0.35 g.). It sublimed *in vacuo* (at 145-50°/0.01 mm). The sublimate crystallised from acetone in shining flakes, m.p. 235°. Hexahydroallosecurinine showed no selective absorption in the UV region. $\lambda_{\max}^{\text{alcohol}}$ 3.01 (OH), 6.19 μ (-N-CO-). [α]_D³⁰ ± 0° (CHCl₃). (Found: C, 69.71; H, 9.23; N, 6.50; H⁺, 0.89. C₁₃H₂₁O₂N requires C, 69.95; H, 9.41; N, 6.37; 2H⁺, 0.84%).

Aromatisation of Allosecurinine to Lactam (III).—To a solution of allosecurinine (1.5 g.) in ethanol (25 ml) H₂SO₄ (conc., 4.5 ml) and zinc dust (3 g.) were added in small portions. The mixture was kept stirred and the solution kept over a water bath for 2 hr. After filtration, the ethanol was removed under suction; it was diluted with water and basified with ammonium hydroxide. The base was extracted with ether and the ether layer worked up in the usual manner. The ether solution on concentration yielded an oily substance. It was purified by chromatography over alumina and was further purified by sublimation. The white sublimate (0.6 g.), thus obtained, crystallised from ether in needles, m.p. 73-74°. [α]_D³⁰ -35° (CHCl₃), $\lambda_{\max}^{\text{alcohol}}$ 6.18 μ (-N-CO-), $\lambda_{\max}^{\text{EtOH}}$ 264 (log ϵ , 2.68) and 274 m μ (log ϵ , 2.58). (Found: C, 77.80; H, 7.35; N, 6.85. C₁₃H₁₅ON requires C, 77.62; H, 7.45; N, 6.97%).

Oxidation of Lactam (III) with Potassium Permanganate.—Lactam (III, 0.3 g.) was dissolved in 1% aqueous KOH to which 5% KMnO₄ solution (aq., 35ml) was added dropwise under stirring and the reaction product was heated on a water bath for 4 hr. After cooling, the solution was filtered from precipitated manganese dioxide. The solution was concentrated *in vacuo* and the residue extracted with ether to remove the neutral components. Finally the aqueous layer was acidified and extracted with chloroform and worked up in the usual manner. The chloroform extract on concentration furnished a white solid (0.04 g.), which on distillation with acetic anhydride furnished phthalic anhydride, m.p. 128° (sublime). (Found: C, 64.96; H, 2.85. Calc. for C₈H₄O₃: C, 64.87; H, 2.72%).

Conversion of Lactam (III) to 1,2,3,4,6,7-Hexahydro-11bH-benzo (a) quinolizine (IV) by LiAlH₄.—A solution of lactam (III, 0.25 g.) in dry ether was added to a suspension of LiAlH₄ (0.25 g.) in absolute ether at 0° and the mixture was stirred at ordinary temperature for 30 hr. The excess reagent was destroyed by moist ether. The ether layer was filtered from the inorganic hydroxides and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. Evaporation of the ether solution left an oily basic substance, IR spectrum of which showed no lactam band. This substance provided a solid hydrochloride, which crystallised from ethanol in needles, m.p. 258-59° (sealed tube), [α]_D³⁰ -82° (EtOH), which was found to be identical with the authentic sample of 1,2,3,4,6,7-hexahydro-11bH-benzo(a)quinolizine hydrochloride;

$\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{EtOH}}$ 265 (log ϵ , 2.64) and 273 m μ (log ϵ , 2.60). (Found: C, 69.78; H, 8.20; N, 6.40; Cl, 15.65. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{17}\text{N}\cdot\text{HCl}$ requires C, 69.82; H, 8.06; N, 6.27; Cl, 15.89%).

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